

God as Point of Light, Ocean of Love, Peace, Bliss, and Happiness: Near-Death Experiences as Empirical Support for Brahma Kumaris Spiritual Education

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Abstract

Near-death experiences (NDEs) give a particular view of how different people from different cultures experience the Divine. Testimonies will always state God as glorious light, the source of unconditional love, peace, bliss, happiness and purity. The paper will examine 22 reported NDEs in Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, Sikhism, Buddhism and Sikhism, as well as the spiritual doctrine of the Brahma Kumaris that God (Shiv Baba) is a point of light and a ocean of love. Results indicate that NDEs empirically endorse the vision of the Supreme of the Brahma Kumaris, which is a universal isotope of divinity and not bound to doctrines.

Keywords: Spiritual Knowledge, Supreme Source, Ocean of Love, Spiritual Education.

1. Introduction

The essence of God has been a matter of debate since centuries, and the traditions provided various theological explanations. However, there are striking similarities in experiential ones, especially in the accounts of near-death experiences. Around the religions, people experience